

Social

STUDY OF EFFECT OF PRE TEACHING TRAINING EXPERIENCE ON STUDENT TEACHERS

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Abstract

Pre teaching practice prepares prospective teachers through teaching practice which has an important role to get prior experience of teaching. When the student teachers begin their career with a high self-efficacy on the classroom instruction and using the teaching methods, teaching aids they are more concerned, ambitious for their task and work harder. The purpose of this study is to find impact of pre teaching on student teachers in terms of teaching qualities.

Keywords: Pre Teaching; Self Efficiency; Teacher Qualities.

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1. Introduction

Pre teaching is an effective method to be applied in the pre-service and in-service stages in the professional development of teachers. Pre teaching is also known as micro teaching. It's an important part of curriculum of teacher training program. It is a valuable instructional tool that mediates between theory and practice. It creates awareness on teachers' behavior, personal habits, and characteristic, teaching acts and techniques, activities and interrelationships with students, problems of structuring and pacing in the classroom. Research showed that student teachers with micro-teaching practice performed better than student teachers who did not have micro-teaching practice prior to their student teaching experience.

Skills learnt in pre teaching help the student teachers to learn the art of teaching at ease and to the maximum extent. The art of teaching involve not only transfer of knowledge from one to other but also facilitates and influences the process of learning. Quality of a teacher is estimated on how much the students understand from his/her teaching. Training of teachers in specific teaching skills is a major challenge in education programs.

The classroom of student teachers cannot be used as a learning platform for acquiring primary teaching skills. The pedagogic skill for teaching can be acquired only through more structured

faculty training techniques. Pre teaching can be practiced with a very small lesson or a single concept and a less number of students. It scales down the complexities of real teaching, as immediate feedback can be sought after each practice session. Pre teaching helps in eliminating errors and builds stronger teaching skills for the beginners and senior teachers. It increases the self-confidence, improves the in-class teaching performances, and develops the classroom management skills.

2. Objective of Study

- Finding of teaching qualities in male student teachers before pre teaching
- Finding of teaching qualities in female student teachers before pre teaching
- Finding of teaching qualities in male student teachers after pre teaching
- Finding of teaching qualities in female student teachers after pre teaching

3. Hypothesis

- 1) There is no influence of pre teaching on male student teachers regarding teaching qualities.
- 2) There is no influence of pre teaching on female student teachers regarding teaching qualities.

4. Methodology

Descriptive survey method was applied for present study. 100 male and 100 female student teachers of 4 teacher training institutes were selected as sample. Before pre teaching students were evaluated for teaching skills using a self prepared test paper. Students were trained for teaching skills and again tested for teaching skills using same test paper. Collected data was tabulated and analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t value statistical tools.

5. Finding and Analysis

Table1: Impact of Pre Teaching on Teaching Qualities of Male Student Teachers

Teaching Parameters	Before Pre Teaching		After Pre Teaching		t-value	Significant Level
	Mean Value	Standard Deviation	Mean Value	Standard Deviation		
Communication Level	28.6	1.24	47.2	1.62	0.69	0.05
Knowledge	66.7	0.82	69.1	1.07	0.23	0.01
Subject Content Continuity	23.4	0.93	38.4	0.82	0.72	0.05
Goal Orientation	21.3	1.08	41.6	0.91	0.82	0.05
Discipline	39.2	0.84	47.2	1.02	0.94	0.05
Curiosity	31.8	0.87	44.7	0.93	0.97	0.05

Table 2: Impact of Pre Teaching on Teaching Qualities of Female Student Teachers

Teaching Parameters	Before Pre Teaching		After Pre Teaching		t-value	Significant Level
	Mean Value	Standard Deviation	Mean Value	Standard Deviation		
Communication Level	27.8	0.87	48.7	0.98	0.84	0.01
Knowledge	69.1	0.93	71.4	0.82	0.32	0.01
Subject Content Continuity	26.2	1.24	39.8	0.62	0.98	0.05
Goal Orientation	23.6	0.93	40.3	1.37	0.73	0.05
Discipline	42.1	0.72	47.3	1.22	0.81	0.01
Curiosity	32.7	0.85	46.8	0.76	1.26	0.05

Figure 1: Impact of Pre Teaching on Teaching Qualities of Male Student Teachers

Figure 2: Impact of Pre Teaching on Teaching Qualities of Female Student Teachers

Result shows that communication level increased from mean value 28.6 to 47.2 after pre teaching training. Knowledge value has not significant difference as variation found 66.7 to 69.1.

Subject content continuity related mean value enhanced from 23.4 to 38.4 showing importance of pre teaching. Goal orientation also observed to grow from 21.3 to 41.6 and student discipline observed to reach from 39.2 to 47.2. Student curiosity also varied from 31.8 mean value to 44.7. Hence hypothesis 1, there is no influence of pre teaching on male student teachers regarding teaching qualities is rejected.

Among female students teachers communication level found to enhance from 27.8 to 48.7 whereas knowledge increased from 69.1 to 71.4 with t value 0.32. Subject content continuity value grows from 26.2 to 39.8 mean value and goal orientation reached to 40.3 from 23.6. Student discipline also observed to increase after pre teaching i.e., 42.1 to 47.3 and curiosity observed to increase 32.7 to 46.8. Thus hypothesis 2, there is no influence of pre teaching on female student teachers regarding teaching qualities is rejected.

6. Conclusion

After pre teaching student teachers found very communicative with the planning process. They found more goal oriented, confident and pre planned. Pre teaching encourages the students in synthesizing information about the topic, technical presentation and student's discipline. Female student teachers are observed as more skillful teachers. It encourages a relationship of motivation and discovered more information between previous and present structured teaching technique.

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